

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

PROJECT TITLE: Resource Waste: An Empirical Study of Repeated Builds During Code Review

RESEARCHER: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

To maintain ethical standards, an application was made on 9-June-2022 and approved on 28-July-2022. [REDACTED] ethics board approved this study and is assigned the number [REDACTED].

Dear Participant,

You are invited to participate in the research project described below.

What is the project about?

The aim of this project is to explore how the recheck command is applied in a practical setting with the OpenStack community. Specifically, We quantitatively analyze (i) how often build failures are rechecked; (ii) the extent to which invoking recheck changes build failure outcomes; and (iii) how much waste is generated by invoking recheck.

In this survey, we are soliciting feedback from the developer community on the perception of using the recheck command during the review process.

Why am I being invited to participate?

The criteria for choosing participants is that they are contributors aged 18+ with recheck experience in a chosen sample of projects hosted on the OpenStack community. Developers with varying experiences will be selected to get a range of responses.

What will I be asked to do?

A simple survey with questions for external contributions to a selected project. These questions will be in the form of multiple choices and open-ended. All questions are worded to be as comprehensive as possible and do not require any complicated thought processes.

How much time will the project take?

Our survey has a total of five sessions to fill out, each session taking no longer than two

minutes to complete.

Are there any risks associated with participating in this project?

No foreseeable risks are associated with participating in this project.

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Can I withdraw from the project?

Participation in this project is completely voluntary. If you agree to participate, you can withdraw from the study at any time. The survey is short and requires little contribution, therefore withdrawal is as easy as closing the survey web page.

What will happen to my information?

The information will be used to strengthen our empirical results and will be produced in an academic paper. Note that no information will lead to any possible privacy breach or identification of participants. The results of the study may be used for a future extension project. All information will be stored on password-encrypted servers at [REDACTED]

Who do I contact if I have questions about the project?

[REDACTED]

If I want to participate, what should I do?

Please agree to the consent form and proceed to fill in the survey. Once completed, press submit to complete the survey.

Yours sincerely,

[REDACTED]

CONSENT FORM

1. I have read the attached information sheet and agree to take part in the following research project: Resource Waste: An Empirical Study of Repeated Builds During Code Review

RESEARCHER:

2. I have had the project, so far as it affects me, fully explained to my satisfaction by the researchers. My consent is given freely.
3. Although I understand the purpose of the research project it has also been explained that involvement may not be of any benefit to me.
4. I have been informed that, while information gained during the study may be published, I will not be identified and my personal results will not be divulged.
5. I understand that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time.
6. I am aware that I should keep a copy of this Consent Form when completed, and the attached Information Sheet.
7. I am over the age of 18.